

Research methodology

Combined effects of pests in farmers' fields: methodological outlines of a yield-loss data base in rice

N. P. Castilla, M. O. Mabbayad, A. T. Barrion, F. A. Elazegui, and S. Savary, IRRI

Farmers' management practices can influence the occurrence of insect pests, diseases, and weeds—the resulting yield losses. Analyzing the combined effects of pests on rice yield is difficult because several pests have to be manipulated and highly variable production situations must be considered. IRRI established a crop-loss data base in 1991 that covers key pests and input factors in irrigated and rainfed lowland rice.

Rice variety PSBRc-4 was planted in 1991 dry season (DS) and C4-137 in

1992 DS in a farmer's field in Laguna Province, Philippines. The farmer's management practices were used. The field in both experiments was divided into three blocks that were superimposed with the following weed treatments 1 wk after transplanting (WAT) rice: infestation with *Echinochloa glabrescens* (5 plants/m²), infestation with *Monochoria vaginalis* (10 plants/m²), and handweeding until rice panicle initiation stage.

Each block had eight microplots consisting of 12 × 12 hills, representing eight randomly assigned pest combinations: bacterial blight (BB), sheath blight (ShB), and yellow stem borer (as deadhearts [DH]); BB and DH; BB and ShB; ShB and DH; ShB only; DH only; BB only; and no pests. High or low pest levels were attained by

artificially infesting or inoculating plots. To establish DH, rice plants were infested with 4-5 egg masses/m² at 3 WAT. Plots were sprayed with 600 ml of BB inoculum (10⁹ colony-forming units/ml) at 1, 2, and 3 WAT. Rice plants at maximum tillering stage were inoculated with ShB by inserting 5 g of a rice hull-grain mixture seeded with the pathogen into the center of each hill. Plots were sprayed daily with water for 1 wk to enhance ShB development.

Pest injuries were assessed at maximum tillering, booting, flowering, and hard dough stages. Prior to statistical analyses, raw data were converted into injury components that best represented the harmful effects of pests (Table 1). Areas under the pest progress curve (AUPPC) for BB, weed infestation above the crop canopy (WA), and weed infestation below the crop canopy (WB) were computed for the period 4-13 WAT.

Multiple regression analyses were performed to describe yield variation using square root transformed pest variables and attainable yield (Ya) as regressors. Ya, which refers to the yield of the control or protected plot in a block, was used as an explanatory variable to account for the varying production situations within and across experiments: varieties, weeds, fertilizer application, and other factors associated with farming practices.

In Table 2, equation 1 indicates that all the injuries manipulated in these experiments, except DH, directly reduced yield, and the equation accounted for 65% of the yield variation. Eighty percent of the yield variation was accounted for when Ya was introduced into the analysis, with 73% attributable

Table 1. Lists of pests and explanatory variables.

Pest	Injury	Acronym	Injury component	Variable
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (yellow stem borer)	Deadhearts	DH	Maximum percentage of tillers with DH throughout the cropping season-	
<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i>	Bacterial blight	BB	Area under BB severity progress curve	Bb
<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	Sheath blight	ShB	Maximum ShB severity throughout the cropping season	Sb
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	Weed infestation (above the crop canopy)	WA	Area under weeds above the crop canopy rating progress curve	Wa
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	Weed infestation (below the crop canopy)	WB	Area under weeds below the crop canopy rating progress curve	Wb

Table 2. Multiple regression equations for the experimental data set.

Equation no.	Variables	Equations ^{a,b}	R ^{2b}
1	Y = f (Dh, Bb, Sb, Wa, Wb)	Y = 7.16 - 0.036 Bb - 0.277 Sb - 0.096 Wa - 0.177 Wb (0.040*) (0.080**) (0.160***) (0.372***)	0.65***
2	Y = f (Ya ^c , Dh, Bb, Sb, Wa, Wb)	Y = 1.00 - 0.911 Ya - 0.200 Dh - 0.219 Sb (0.728***) (0.026*) (0.041**)	0.80***
3	Y = f (Ya, Ya × Dh, Ya × Bb, Ya × Sb, Ya × Wa, Ya × Wb)	Y = -0.31 + 1.166 Ya - 0.038 Ya × Dh - 0.044 Ya × Sb (0.728***) (0.027*) (0.034*)	0.79***

^a Values in parentheses refer to the partial R² of each variable. ^b *, **, *** = significant at the 5, 1, and .01% levels, respectively. ^c Ya = attainable yield.

to Ya alone (Equation 2). Equation 3 further shows that increasing pest injuries, specifically ShB and DH, are associated with more than a proportional reduction in yield. Equation 3 demonstrates more generally that the

attainable yield, which represents the production levels, interacts with pest injuries in the descriptive damage function generated by the two experiments. Our data to date show that production levels—yield outcome of

farmers' management practices, inputs, and environmental factors—interact with pest injuries in damage functions and must be considered in pest management. ■

A simple methodology for analyzing rice sheath blight (ShB) epidemiologic processes under semicontrolled conditions

R. M. Leafio and N. P. Castilla, IRRRI; D. B. Lapis, Plant Pathology Department, University of the Philippines at Los Baños; and S. Savary, IRRRI

We developed a simple and reproducible methodology to study ShB epidemics under semicontrolled environmental conditions. It involves two basic components: 1) an analogue of a standing crop that can be manipulated according to the environmental variables being investigated, and 2) a probe that allows monitoring and quantification of ShB conduciveness in this manipulated environment.

The crop analogue is a quadrat of 3×3 hills (see figure). At maximum tillering stage, all hills in the quadrats except the center hill—are inoculated with a rice hull/grain mixture colonized by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn to serve as source plants. The center hill is removed after inoculation and replaced with a healthy trap plant that was grown in an adjacent, disease-free area. The trap plant serves as a probe. After 3 d of exposure, the trap plant is transferred into a pot. ShB severity is measured, and emerging infection points are counted. The procedure can be used in a series of replications and for several treatments. It can be repeated over time with successive batches of trap plants.

Leaf wetness duration can be manipulated by covering the quadrat with plastic cages for different amounts of time. Crop density can be varied by planting hills at different spacings. The number and position of ShB lesions in the canopy can be manipulated by varying the amount and positioning of the inoculum. Trap plants can be grown in plots with

different N input levels to vary their N content; and different varieties can also be compared.

Data are analyzed using repeated-measures ANOVA. The table shows the format of an ANOVA where the log-transformed number of ShB infection points is analyzed in an experiment with three replications, eight treatments, and three batches. The treatments represent different combinations of inoculum amount and positioning (see figure).

The results indicate that the positioning of inoculum has a significant effect on the number of infection points. Estimates of treatment means are T1: 122 a; T2: 64 b; T3: 82 a; T4: 111 a; T5: 37 b; T6: 147 a; T7: 150 a; and T8: 20 c, where values followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to DMRT

($p < 0.05$). Further comparison of means shows significantly less infection points when inoculum was placed at the stem level only. A two- to fourfold increase in infection points occurred when the inoculum was placed at the leaf level. Increasing the amount of inoculum from 2.5 to 5.0 g did not significantly increase the number of infection points. The number is significantly lower in the third batch than in the first two batches, suggesting a decline in infection efficiency over time. Spontaneous infections are measured on the control trap plants (T8), which provide a measure of the 'background noise' specific to each experiment.

This methodology can be used to address several driving variables in the rice-ShB pathosystem. ■

Format of a repeated-measures ANOVA for the log-transformed number of infection points per trap plant. The experiment involves 5 replications, 8 treatments, and 3 batches.

Source of variation	df	Example			
		df	F _{obs}	F _{0.05}	Conservative F _{0.05} ^a
Replication	r-1	4	6.23	2.71	2.71
Treatments (T) ^b	t-1	7	12.4	2.36	2.36
Control vs other treatments (U)	u-1	1	54.5	4.20	4.20
Among other treatments (V)	v-1	6	5.43	2.44	2.44
T7 vs T1 to T6 (W)	w-1	1	7.79	4.20	4.20
Among T1 to T6 (X)	x-1	5	4.96	2.56	2.56
Inoculum positioning (P)	p-1	2	11.6	3.34	3.34
Inoculum amount (A)	a-1	1	0.00	4.20	4.20
P x A	(p-1)(a-1)	2	12.4	3.34	3.34
Error (a)	(r-1)(t-1)	28			
Batch (B)	b-1	2	4.31	3.14	3.99
T x B	(t-1)(b-1)	14	1.68	1.85	2.15
(Control vs other treatments) x B	(u-1)(b-1)	2	4.90	3.14	3.99
(Among other treatments) x B	(v-1)(b-1)	12	1.14	1.90	2.24
(T7 vs T1 to T6) x B	(w-1)(b-1)	2	0.01	3.14	3.99
(Among T1 to T6) x B	(x-1)(b-1)	10	1.36	1.98	2.36
P x B	(p-1)(b-1)	4	2.88	2.51	3.14
A x B	(a-1)(b-1)	2	0.74	3.14	3.99
P x A x B	(p-1)(a-1)(b-1)	4	3.1	2.51	3.14
Error (b)	t(r-1)(b-1)	64			

^a Based on batch df = 1. The conservative F values are usually considered. ^b The treatments represent different combinations of amount and positioning of inoculum: T1: 2.5 g at leaf level, T2: 2.5 g at stem level, T3: 2.5 g at stem level and 2.5 g at leaf level, T4: 5.0 g at leaf level, T5: 5.0 g at stem level, T6: 5.0 g at stem level and 5.0 g at leaf level, T7: 5.0 g at stem level and 2.5 g at leaf level, and T8: control.